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A TOP LINE PRODUCT PROGRESSING TOWARDS ITS DOOM: A BRIEF CASE STUDY ON MAGGI

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ABSTRACT

This case study discusses in depth the growth, success and decline of a noodle market giant Nestle's Maggi. This case discusses its growth in Indian market wherein consumer psyche was against any kind of junk food and that too noodles made of white flour. But Maggi's product features and easy cooking method along with its marketing strategies and long product line made it not only a very popular but a monopolistic brand. But due to some mistakes and malfunctioning it fell into controversies. This case discusses that how a brand can get sabotaged and crash in the market if it doesn't follow the legalities and proves to be harmful for the consumers because today's consumer is very clever and well informed about its rights and government norms.

Key words: Nestle's Maggi, noodles, junk food

INTRODUCTION: HISTORY OF THE TWO MINUTE NOODLES

Julius Michel Johannes Maggi introduced a formula to enhance the taste in meals. The brand Maggi was first established in 1863 in Switzerland and it came into market in 1872 when his father's mill was taken over by Julius Maggi. There were plenty of jobs for women at the factory at the time of the industrial revolution. They faced a problem while preparing meals. Therefore, Julius created a vegetable product as asked by the Swiss Public Welfare society, that would be speedy to prepare and easily digestible. He came with two instant pea soups and bean soup and then after reached the pinnacle of success. In 1947 Maggi merged with Nestle India then came up with the Maggie 2-minute instant noodles on witnessing an increase in the number of women workforce in 1980s^[1].

MAGGI: A HEALTHY PRODUCT LIFE CYCLE

During 1980s when the brand was launched there was no direct challenge from instant noodles rather the competition came from other snacks that made Indian food widely famous. The factor that differentiated the two eatables was the hygiene factor. Maggi positioned itself as the healthy brand. It first targeted working women but later on through surveys they came to know that children are the larger consumer of the instant noodles. After its repositioning, it targeted children through various promotional tools such as sketch pens, colour pencils, and fun books to entice children. And this worked splendidly for the brand. In the initial years, Maggi's annual development grew by 15%, and today Maggi is the foremost brand in the instant noodles division in India, with a marketplace share of 79.3%. The worth of Maggi today is Rs.200 crores and it is 10% Nestle India's top line. It has taken time to interpret the consumer psyche and has established itself as the utmost successful brand^[2].

OUTGROWING ITS COMPETITORS:

Maggi was the market pioneer in instant noodles segment. It has given a boost and a first force advantage over the other brands. It has widened its market since then by introducing a lot of variants. Maggi has introduced Vegetable and Dal Atta noodles to gratify to those who are health conscious. Maggi's products come in travel packs as well as bulk packs, to cater to those who look for convenience while travelling and those who are price sensitive and prefer to purchase food in bulk. Joono Simon, ECD of Ogilvy Bengaluru says, "For anyone who grew up in the 80s and 90s, Maggi is a reminder of their youth. The days of humble origins, midnight hunger in the hostels of the university". Youth has got the correct start up with the 'Fast to Cook, Good to Eat' campaign. In 2005 Nestle emerged with a new variant that targeted the health conscience people. They reinvigorated the product with calcium and protein and thus, came the TASTE BHI AND HEALTH BHI campaign. They raised challenge against the common principle that whatever is healthy is not tasty. Another huge move was, when it introduced ME AUR MERI MAGGI CAMPAIGN with Amitabh Bachchan. After the campaign, Maggi had it all, from taste to health to happiness. It became an unbeatable brand^[3].

ADVERTISING STRATEGIES

Maggi promoted its product by:

1. Distributing free samples.
2. Giving gifts to the delivery of empty packages.
3. The dry sample packet distribution Maggi
4. Wet Sampling – Dispensing prepared Maggi.
5. Accessibility in various packages 50gm, 100gm, 200gm, etc.. And
6. Definite tagline communication

Over its ads, Nestle's Maggi positioned as a "fun" food for children that mothers can easily prepare. Phrases like "Mommy, bhokh Lagi Hai" (Mom, I'm hungry), "Bas 2 Minutes" and "Fast to cook, Good to eat" product communicated effectively to guide consumers. [⁴]

It also introduced its variants to acquire maximum share of the market. The range of the product line under it starts with its Noodles which comes in different quantity packages (from a very small package of INR 5 to the family 6 piece packs) and Maggi Aata Noodles was also launched (made up of whole wheat) for the people who don't find white floor noodles healthy. Similarly, different soups of Maggi were introduced in the market and have given neck to neck challenge to the market leader of package soups market Knorr. Maggi's Tomato Sauce is also a leading product which again comes in different packaging right from big size glass bottles to small sachets. They have also introduced refill packs in big size sachet with a threaded cap. Another variant was the introduction of Maggi Imli Pichkoo (tamarind Sauce) which every Indian is fond of eating with ethnic fast food like Samosa, Kachori, Kofta etc.. Its product line includes other products like Cup Mania, Different flavours of Maggi pasta etc..

Figure A:

SOME MAGGI VARIANTS

BRAND ENDORSEMENTS

The government said, "Any brand ambassador or a superstar to endorse products or services is responsible for the action if an ad is misleading. The government supposed celebrities including stars, Madhuri Dixit and Preity Zinta are legally accountable, if found ads for widely held Maggi noodles to mislead consumers. According to (FSSAI) act, anyone who is party to a misleading advertisement or publication can be fined up to Rs 10 lakh. The anticipated amendments to the Consumer Protection Act has provisions for the issue of the direction of removing this type of advertising, even reporting such desecrations to the police or any other law implementing agency for criminal prosecution , "says a report in the Times of India. The amount of the fine FSSAI is ridiculous and is not a deterrent, considering endorsement of brand run into crores; the more important question is whether the brand ambassador should be held responsible - and who else should it be?^[8]

PENETRATION INTO RURAL AND LOWER MIDDLE CLASS SEGMENTS OF CUSTOMERS

"Nestle India's Maggi has reduced the sales margin at Rs 5 packet Maggi noodles to 8%as against 9% earlier , however , the lower margin of 9 percent is retained in other Maggi noodles SKUs (Stock -keeping units) . In addition, Nestle has reduced gram mage of Rs 5 pack 35g from 40g front before. Analyst Karvy Naveen Trivedi said, In the recent years, consumer goods companies in India have launched small packages of food and personal care products at a price of Rs 5, Rs10, etc. move quickly and directed primarily to groups lower income and rural population, in an attempt to expand and grow faster, as competition has increased.^[9] And to promote this in rural areas who could have been a more trusted celebrity in India other than the actor Amitabh Bachchan.

Figure B:

The new “Me and Meri Maggi” Campaign with Amitabh Bachchan was inclined towards portraying Maggi as an integral part of the life style of a common middle class and lower middle class segment of India. The ad campaign designed follows a storytelling style through an ad commercial using emotional appeals by a trusted superstar of the country. It was intended that it can create the desired interest in the viewers which makes them watch the full advertisement. It is very good example of Chotu Maggi (small package of Maggi) where bollywood star Mr. Amitabh Bachchan sits under a tree in a village narrating story of a village boy whose hunger strikes were affectionately responded to by his mother with a small and cheap pack of Maggi.

ACCUSATIONS

As per the Central Food Safety Authority of India the removal of 9 variants of Maggi noodles have been ordered after the Ministry of Health confirmed that Nestle has ignored safety guidelines. According to JP Nadda Union Minister, his department acknowledged lab reports from all the states and the reports has led the Indian government to pull back the nine variants of Maggi after incriminating evidence suggesting Nestle India has abandoned standards by the food security established by the country. ^[5]

" Remove and recover all nine of its approved variants Maggi noodles have been found on the market unsafe and dangerous for consumption , and stop the production, processing , importation, distribution and sale of that product with immediate effect ,"^[6]

Nadda said "We have reached the conclusion that the safety and food standards have not joined Nestle Maggi Company and products, so we have given instructions that all nine products (variants) must be withdrawn from the market."

Nestle India launched Maggi Oats Noodles without receiving the approval of the authorities. The company noteven cared to undertake risk and safety assessment. FSSAI has well-ordered the instant withdrawal of Maggi Oats noodles. ^[7]

ACCUSATIONS ON NESTLE’S BRAND MAGGI

On March 26, 2014 Government Regional Public Analyst Laboratory on the Baba Raghav Das Medical College campus in Gorakhpur, it was this lab that detected excessive amounts of monosodium glutamate (MSG), flavor

enhancer in Maggi. It led to a nationwide scandal causing Nestle to drag out the item from the shelves. One of six laboratories for food analysis throughout the state, the Gorakhpur facility serves 15 districts of Basti, Devipatan, Gorakhpur and Faizabadmandals .The mandal includes Barabanki Faizabad, where the samples were submitted.^[10]

Figure C:

Three main violations by the FSSAI:

- Occurrence of Lead identified in product in excess of the maximum permissible levels of 2.5 ppm.
- Misleading labeling information on the package reading “No added MSG”, and
- Release of a non-standardized food product in the market, viz. “Maggi Oats Masala Noodles with Tastemaker” without risk assessment and grant of product approval.

THE ILL FORTUNES OF THE BRAND

The euro monitor report says that Maggi annual sales of the instant noodles last year was 60%. Maggi was a cash cow for Nestle. After the food safety and drug administration of the state of Uttar Pradesh detected excessive levels and lead and the flavour enhancer monosodium glutamate the sales dipped by 20% and nestle India posted a loss in 15 years. The net loss was detected and the net loss accounted for 64.4crore for the quarter. According to the Wharton management professor John Kimberly, it is the responsibility of the parent company to look for its products and brands. If a company faces such a situation it calls for a quick and measured response. It was observed by researches that FDI in Uttar Pradesh recalled Maggi in April 30, it was the month of June when Nestle finally addressed the media in Delhi. A five point crisis management strategy was recommended by John Kimberly to tackle such situations and restore credibility. In many cases the

companies fail to understand the gravity of the situation and delay in handling the problem. This paves a way for many discrepancies in creep in.^[11]

CONSUMER REACTIONS TOWARDS THE CONTROVERSIES:

Once the jurisdiction found Maggi Noodles guilty of the charges put on it Maggi evaluated its products stocked in the retail outlets to be worth Rs. 320 crore. Nestle India got maximum part of it incinerated at five cement factories across India into fuel.

But even before that would happen the Indian national groups of people had started rallies in India agitating against the product and they burnt packets of Maggi on every street.

It was claimed that the recalling of the product was one of the largest in the history of Indian food industry. Luca Fichera, Vice-President, said that it was an immensely complex and mammoth activity but they wanted to complete it as fast as possible owing to the customer's trust. Almost 27,420 tonnes of Maggi noodles were recalled from the market.

Figure D:

WINNING OVER THE GOVERNMENT AND CONSUMER

The multinationals abide by the rules of the land. If the rules are found inadequate they do not adhere to follow the same protocols and standards that they do in their own country. Therefore it is the duty of the government to set adequate rules and regulations in order to maintain the food and safety standards. Companies in the processed food segment have suffered a hit after the Maggi ban. The Knorr and Top ramen brands of Hindustan Unilever and Indo Nissin foods respectively also took their products off the shelves after nestle withdrew Maggi

As for the brand revival, communication is the key, unless the brand comes out and addresses the consumer regarding the problem, it will only get bigger. If the brand wants to survive in the long run, it should start talking to the consumers and show that it cares for the wellbeing of the consumers. The test results should be made public, till the ban is removed the ingredients on which the entire issue is based should be displayed on billboards, posters and banners. The brand is very popular among the people so with the correct measures the company can revive the brand. There have been many cases in which brands with a perfectly healthy product lifecycle has suffered a hit in the market but they were able to regain the trust and have re-established themselves. In a study conducted by Millward Brown last year Maggi ranked number 18 in BrandZ Top 50

Most valuable Indian brand study and it then had a valuation of \$1,127 million. With the appropriate crisis management strategies the brand is likely to come back and regain its earlier market share.^[12]

EFFECT ON SIMILAR PRODUCTS

As per the national company CEO, the sale of instant noodles has dropped by more than ¾%. Since it is impossible to say that how long it is going to last. Other brand like Yippee and Top Ramen are banned in states like Tamil Nadu, Gujrat, Uttarakhand, Assam and J&K as a consequence of the Maggi case. Retailers have removed their stocks of other Maggi products, and there is a 50% drop in sale of Maggi pasta. After the ban the perceptions for the other products in the instant noodle segment have suffered, consumer hesitates in buying other noodles with regard to the Maggi case.^[13]

CONTROVERSIES OF OTHER PRODUCTS IN THE FOOD SEGMENT

The Maggi noodles has created a controversy rage in the food space. While local restaurants have not stopped selling their versions extravagant Maggi, many people are turning away with a heavy heart. This is not the first time a food product has been under strict scanner of government officials. Some of the more popular brands have had their share of sleepless nights in the past. Some of the renowned controversies of food product are:^[14]

The Dairy milk:

Dairy milk one of the famous chocolate faced the wrath of angry parents and loyal customers over the report of worms found in Cadbury's Dairy Milk in Maharashtra in 2003. The reason behind this causes was the improper packaging of the product. In 2004 it spent a huge sum of amount to get imported machinery to ensure better packing and packaging.

McDonalds:

McDonald has been making news for all the wrong reasons for quite some time. From a dead mouse in the cold coffee from a person in Canada for dental material, human teeth and other items in the "Happy Meals", the brand has had a turbulent journey. Their sales plummeted after the scandal food security in China, when it was alleged that McDonald provider Hushi Shanghai food Co. packed expired meat.

Restaurants stopped using the Shanghai and many of McDonald's outlets failed to provide some products, including Big Macs and Chicken McNuggets. There were also reports of people finding plastic materials in their chicken nuggets in Japan. The company has recently stated to phase out the use of meat chickens injected antibiotics.

KFC:

In India, in a scandal of food security related to rice, the Safety Authority and Food Standards of India (FSSAI) had said samples 'Rizo Rice' taken KFC Scindia House in Connaught Place showed that it is containing artificial color.

In defense, KFC had declared: "The recent news reports on KFC rice being unsafe is a case of misinformation only use natural colour (betacarotene), which are obtained from renowned international suppliers in our meals.

Rizo rice. We are sure our product quality and are working closely with regulatory authorities in this matter that have ensured that the sample is safe for consumption and no proceedings have been initiated against KFC . "

Coca- cola& Pepsi:

Everyone wondered what the secret of carbonated beverages that have such a good taste? Well, the government did. In 1977, when the government of India Coke questioned about his "secret recipe "there was no response from the company.

According to a report in the New York Times, presented in 2006, dispute revolves around companies, cola with pesticides was reported for the first time in 2003. It rose again in 2006 when an environmental group called Center science and Environment said that sodas sold by Pepsi and Coca -Cola are laced with pesticides.

ADVERTISING STRATEGIES OF SIMILAR PRODUCTS

After the ban of Maggi, Yippee and the other competitors changed its advertising campaign in order to ensure consumer that noodles are safe for consumption. It came up with different educational advertisement assuring the safety of the product .This brand has taken initiatives to educate consumers regarding the MSG, lead and glutamate. Recently it has developed individual videos on important topics such as:

- How is quality ensured in each packet of Yippee! Noodles?
- What ingredients go into Yippee Noodles?
- Where can I find the testing reports for Yippee!?

Yippee has also introduced ' you ask answer ' TVC, where in case of any query, customers can call the toll-free number or visit the website of the company. Initially, retailers and distributors were given flyers by ITC stating that "Yippee! Noodles are safe ' to be given to customers ^[15].

STRATEGY FOR BRAND REVIVAL

Regaining its position in a market is quite a job when the consumer perspective has changed. Nestle has to formulate strategies in order to win back its consumers and the new product should meet the regulations and standards of India. Once this is done, the brand can build up its value slowly by fulfilling its CSR and good public relations. It will be important to develop connection with stakeholders in order to communicate a message that helps them emotionally to manage reputation. Accepting the mistake and promising that such an incident would be never repeated is the correct way to move forward for the Nestle product Maggi. In order to revive the brand image the customer and investor's trust is the key element. Consumer performance leads to show the parameter of business performance. Nestle in the press conference said that they are going to do all the things in order to tackle the situation. As adding to this statement "we will do our best to clarify the confusion along with our stakeholders." Soon Maggi is going to comeback although it is a very tough job. ^[16]

CONCLUSION

As per this case study, Nestle's Maggi which has been one of the strongest product in the noodle market and has had a monopoly in the market was always praised by the marketers for a long

product life cycle that it has had. Apart from its features which was mainly taste and fast to took and easy to eat its marketing strategies have supported its growth in the market. But due to some of its mistakes and wrong steps that it was found guilty in the legal aspects. Today's consumer being very powerful and well informed this noodle market's giant was dragged in the court for judgement and finally got banned in India.

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